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**STATUS OF GENDER AND DEVELOPMENT MAINSTREAMING PRACTICES IN THE
MANAGEMENT OF PUBLIC SCHOOLS IN ALABAT ISLAND, DIVISION OF QUEZON:
BASIS FOR AN ENHANCED MAINSTREAMING PLAN**

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the status of Gender and Development (GAD) mainstreaming practices in public schools at Alabat Island, Division of Quezon, as a basis for developing an enhanced gender mainstreaming plan. While GAD mainstreaming is a policy priority, there was a lack of understanding about its actual implementation and the challenges faced in schools. The study sought to examine the level of awareness of GAD mainstreaming among school stakeholders, the extent of its implementation, the challenges encountered, and to propose an intervention plan to enhance gender-responsive practices. A descriptive research design was employed, utilizing a survey questionnaire to gather data from school heads, GAD Coordinators, and members of the GAD Technical Working Group. Data analysis included ranking, mean, and standard deviation. GAD implementers demonstrated high awareness of GAD mainstreaming, particularly regarding gender-responsive policies. However, familiarity with gender-sensitive teaching strategies and gender-responsive budgeting was lower. While GAD practices were fully implemented, policy integration into school governance was more established than the use of gender-sensitive teaching materials and strategies. Resource constraints, cultural resistance, and institutional challenges were identified as significant barriers to full implementation. The study highlights the need for structured implementation, continuous training, consistent monitoring and evaluation, and policy reinforcement to promote gender inclusivity in education. The proposed Gender Mainstreaming Plan aims to address identified gaps by enhancing capacity-building programs, strengthening policy implementation, securing funding, and increasing stakeholder engagement. This will contribute to expanding awareness, improving instructional integration of gender concepts, and ensuring the sustainability of gender-responsive practices in schools.

Keywords: *Gender Mainstreaming, Gender Awareness, Gender Stereotypes, Public Schools, Capacity Building, Policy Implementation*

INTRODUCTION

Integrating Gender and Development (GAD) practices into educational management is a fundamental strategy for achieving equity, inclusivity, and social transformation. The 1987 Philippine Constitution articulates the state's responsibility to promote gender equality and acknowledges the essential role of women in national development. This is further strengthened by Republic Act No. 9710, also known as the Magna Carta of Women, which institutionalizes gender mainstreaming as a key mechanism for achieving gender equality across all government sectors, including education. Despite the presence of such legal frameworks, there remains a significant gap between policy and practice, especially in educational institutions where gender-responsive systems are crucial yet inconsistently implemented.

The Department of Education (DepEd), through various issuances such as DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2017, has set guidelines for promoting gender-responsive basic education. However, these efforts often lack comprehensive mechanisms for implementation, monitoring, and evaluation. Republic Act No. 10533 or the Enhanced Basic Education Act, while advocating inclusive education, also falls short in articulating concrete strategies for gender-responsive curriculum delivery and school governance. These gaps in execution underscore the need for a more localized and practical understanding of how GAD is mainstreamed in schools.

While the Philippines has made strides in promoting gender equality in education, key challenges persist ranging from limited awareness and understanding of gender concepts among educators and school leaders, to cultural resistance and resource limitations. However, these challenges present valuable opportunities. Lack of awareness can be addressed through sustained capacity-building efforts, as emphasized by Lualhati (2019) and Mendoza (2020), who advocate for continuous training on gender integration in curriculum and pedagogy. Resistance rooted in sociocultural norms can be transformed through dialogue, mentorship, and community engagement, fostering deeper appreciation for inclusive education.

The findings of this study also resonate with Santos (2022), who stressed the role of school leadership and community involvement in strengthening gender-responsive practices. Similarly, reports from the Philippine Commission on Women (2022) highlight the need to optimize collaborations with NGOs and government agencies to bridge funding gaps and enhance program reach. UNESCO (2020) further emphasizes that empowering local stakeholders through inclusive training and mentorship can result in sustainable and scalable GAD initiatives.

In this context, the study aims not only to assess the current state of GAD implementation but also to design actionable recommendations that can inform an enhanced gender mainstreaming plan for public schools in Alabat Island. Through this, the research hopes to contribute meaningfully to the ongoing national and local efforts in achieving gender equality in education not just in policy, but in practice and everyday school life.

This study investigates the current status of GAD mainstreaming practices in the management of public schools in Alabat Island, Division of Quezon. Rather than focusing solely on deficiencies, the research adopts a strengths-based approach, aiming to identify existing good practices, challenges, and areas for enhancement. It seeks to provide a holistic picture of how gender equality principles are applied in school management, policy implementation, teacher training, stakeholder engagement, and curriculum integration. The ultimate goal is to formulate an enhanced mainstreaming plan that supports sustainable, inclusive, and gender-responsive education at the local level.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the status of gender and development mainstreaming practices in the management of public schools in Alabat Island, Division of Quezon, which serves as the basis for an enhanced mainstreaming plan. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the status of Gender and Development mainstreaming practices in terms of:
 - 1.1 Level of awareness of GAD implementers regarding gender concepts and their practical application in classrooms and school policies;
 - 1.2 Level of understanding among Alabat public schools' GAD implementers regarding traditional gender stereotypes and biases; and
 - 1.3 Level of implementation of policies, programs and activities as to governance and instruction?
2. What are the problems encountered in GAD mainstreaming practices?
3. What solutions are applied by GAD implementers to address the problems encountered?
4. What gender mainstreaming plan can be proposed to enhance GAD mainstreaming practices among the public schools on the island of Alabat, Division of Quezon?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research design to assess the current status of Gender and Development (GAD) mainstreaming practices in the management of public schools within Alabat Island, Division of Quezon. The approach allowed for a systematic examination of existing practices, identification of patterns, and establishment of relationships among variables through data collected from 90 respondents comprised of one school head, one GAD coordinator, and one GAD Technical Working Group (TWG) member per school. A structured survey questionnaire served as the main research instrument and was divided into three key sections: awareness and understanding of gender concepts, challenges encountered in mainstreaming GAD, and the solutions adopted by focal persons. The responses

were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, and mean calculations to address the first set of research problems related to awareness, understanding, and implementation. To evaluate the problems encountered (Statement of the Problem 2), mean and standard deviation were computed, while the third problem, concerning solutions applied by GAD implementers, was examined through the use of mean, standard deviation, and weighted mean.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Part I. Status of Gender and Development Mainstreaming Practice

Table 1

Level of Awareness of GAD Implementers Regarding Gender Concepts and their Practical Application in Classrooms and School Policies

Question	SH		GADC		GAD TWG		TOTAL		VI
	RCR	%	RCR	%	RCR	%	RCR	%	
1. Meaning of GPB	27.00	90.00	28.00	93.33	30.00	100.00	85.00	94.40	VHA
2. Full form of GAD AR	27.00	90.00	20.00	66.67	21.00	70.00	68.00	75.60	HA
3. Description of AOM	6.00	20.00	6.00	20.00	1.00	3.33	13.00	14.40	VLA
4. Meaning of GFPS	14.00	46.67	22.00	73.33	18.00	60.00	54.00	60.00	HA
5. Use of GMEF	25.00	83.33	29.00	96.67	28.00	93.33	82.00	91.10	VHA
6. Representation of GST	25.00	83.33	27.00	90.00	28.00	93.33	80.00	88.90	VHA
7. Meaning of VAW	30.00	100.00	28.00	93.33	30.00	100.00	88.00	97.80	VHA
8. Representation of MOVE	22.00	73.33	24.00	80.00	19.00	63.33	65.00	72.20	HA
9. Meaning of MCW	29.00	96.67	29.00	96.67	29.00	96.67	87.00	96.70	VHA
10. Involvement in PAPs	25.00	83.33	19.00	63.33	15.00	50.00	59.00	65.60	HA
11. Meaning of gender in GAD	11.00	36.67	9.00	30.00	12.00	40.00	32.00	35.60	LA
12. Integration of gender into classroom practices	4.00	13.33	8.00	26.67	8.00	26.67	20.00	22.20	LA
13. Practical strategies for promoting gender equality in school policies	29.00	96.67	24.00	80.00	26.00	86.67	79.00	87.80	VHA
14. Importance of providing comprehensive sexuality education	22.00	73.33	19.00	63.33	22.00	73.33	63.00	70.00	HA

15. Role of teachers in preventing and addressing gender-based violence in schools	30.00	100.00	30.00	100.00	30.00	100.00	90.00	100.00	VHA
16. Schools in ensuring equal participation and representation of girls and boys in all areas of education	29.00	96.67	28.00	93.33	30.00	100.00	87.00	96.70	VHA
17. Parents and the wider community involvement in promoting gender equality	30.00	100.00	28.00	93.33	29.00	96.67	87.00	96.70	VHA
18. The purpose of gender sensitivity training for teachers and staff	27.00	90.00	25.00	83.33	30.00	100.00	82.00	91.11	VHA
19. Schools creating an inclusive environment for LGBTQ+ students	27.00	90.00	26.00	86.67	26.00	86.67	79.00	87.80	VHA
20. The purpose of the GAD Focal Point System in schools	29.00	96.67	29.00	96.67	29.00	96.67	87.00	96.70	VHA
Mean	23.4	78.00	22.9	76.33	23.05	76.83			
Interpretation		HA		HA		HA	69.35	77.07	HA

Levels	Frequency	Percentage
Very High Awareness	31	34.45
High Awareness	55	61.11
Moderate Awareness	3	3.33
Low Awareness	0	0.00
Very Low Awareness	1	1.11
Total	90	100.00

Legends:

Abbreviation	Meaning	Percentage (%)	Range	Verbal Interpretation
RCR	Respondents' Correct Responses	80-100		Very High Awareness (VHA)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	60-79		High Awareness (HA)
SH	School Heads	40-59		Moderate Awareness (MA)
GADC	Gender and Development Coordinators	20-39		Low Awareness (LA)
GADTWG	Gender and Development Technical Working Group	0-19		Very Low Awareness (VLA)

Table 1 reveals that the overall level of awareness of the 90 respondents comprising school heads, GAD Coordinators, and GAD TWG members on gender concepts and their application in classrooms and school policies is classified as High Awareness (HA) with an overall mean score of 69.35%. A majority (61.11%) demonstrated high awareness, while 34.45% showed very high awareness (VHA), highlighting the effectiveness of existing capacity-building programs. Respondents showed strong knowledge in areas such as gender-related policies, gender sensitivity training, and violence prevention, with several items (e.g., Questions 1, 5, 6, 7, 9, 13, 15–20) scoring above 80%. Notably, Question 15 scored 100%, indicating full

awareness of teachers' roles in addressing gender-based violence. However, areas such as the GAD Annual Report, community involvement, and MOVE representation reflected slightly lower scores (60–79%), pointing to areas needing improvement. Alarming, Low Awareness (20–39%) was noted in Questions 11 and 12, while Very Low Awareness (14.40%) was seen in Question 3, indicating significant gaps in understanding the Audit Observation Memo (AOM), gender integration in teaching, and core gender definitions. The results suggest that while foundational awareness is strong, especially in policy advocacy, practical classroom application and gender budgeting remain weak spots. These findings underscore the need for sustained, targeted GAD training focusing on instructional integration, financial alignment, and community-based gender initiatives to ensure meaningful and holistic gender mainstreaming in schools.

Table 2

Level of Understanding Among GAD Implementers Regarding Traditional Gender Stereotypes and Biases

Question	SH		GADC		GAD TWG		TOTAL		VI
	RCR	%	RCR	%	RCR	%	RCR	%	
1. Impact of traditional gender biases impact to students in Philippine public schools	13.00	43.33	13.00	43.33	19.00	63.33	45.00	50.00	MU
2. Effect of traditional gender biases on teacher-student interactions	11.00	36.67	14.00	46.67	14.00	46.67	39.00	43.00	MU
3. GAD coordinators addressing traditional gender biases in Philippine public schools address traditional gender biases in educational policies and programs	24.00	80.00	28.00	93.33	26.00	86.67	78.00	86.70	VHU
4. Importance of GAD coordinators advocating gender-sensitive education	28.00	93.33	27.00	90.00	23.00	76.67	78.00	86.70	VHU
5. Contribution of GAD coordinators in creating a more inclusive learning environment for all students	23.00	76.67	21.00	70.00	22.00	73.33	66.00	73.30	HU
6. Common gender stereotypes prevalent in Philippine society that GAD coordinators need to address in educational settings	19.00	63.33	14.00	46.67	15.00	50.00	48.00	53.30	MU
7. GAD coordinators fostering a culture of gender equality and inclusivity among students and staff	29.00	96.67	24.00	80.00	30.00	100.00	83.00	92.20	VHU

8. Impact of traditional gender biases on career choices among students	17.00	56.67	17.00	56.67	14.00	46.67	48.00	53.30	MU
9. GAD coordinators crucial dismantling traditional gender biases	22.00	73.33	18.00	60.00	17.00	56.67	57.00	63.30	HU
10. Common stereotypes perpetuated by traditional gender biases in Philippine public schools	21.00	70.00	20.00	66.67	15.00	50.00	56.00	62.20	HU
11. Coordinators promoting gender-sensitive language use in educational settings in the Philippines	26.00	86.67	28.00	93.33	27.00	90.00	81.00	90.00	VHU
12. Role of GAD coordinators in addressing gender disparities	28.00	93.33	30.00	100.00	30.00	100.00	88.00	97.80	VHU
13. Effect of traditional gender biases to decision-making processes in school governance	15.00	50.00	20.00	66.67	14.00	46.67	49.00	54.40	MU
14. Strategies of GAD coordinators to promote gender equality in curriculum development	26.00	86.67	24.00	80.00	26.00	86.67	76.00	84.40	VHU
15. Importance of addressing traditional gender biases in student assessments	27.00	90.00	25.00	83.33	28.00	93.33	80.00	88.90	VHU
16. Advocating for safe and inclusive school environments for all genders	21.00	70.00	22.00	73.33	28.00	93.33	71.00	78.90	HU
17. Ways GAD coordinators address traditional gender biases in teacher professional development programs	21.00	70.00	27.00	90.00	26.00	86.67	74.00	82.20	VHU
18. Impact of traditional gender biases to students' access to extracurricular opportunities	15.00	50.00	16.00	53.33	13.00	43.33	44.00	48.90	MU
19. Role of GAD coordinators in promoting gender equality in parent-teacher interactions	29.00	96.67	29.00	96.67	26.00	86.67	84.00	93.30	VHU
20. Collaboration of GAD coordinators collaborate with student organizations to challenge traditional gender biases	30.00	100.00	27.00	90.00	29.00	96.67	86.00	95.60	VHU
Weighted Mean	22.25	74.17	22.20	74.00	22.10	73.67	66.55	73.92	HU
Interpretation		HU		HU		HU			
Level				Frequency				Percent	
With Very High Understanding				36				40.00	
With High Understanding				31				34.45	
With Moderate Understanding				19				21.11	
With Less Understanding				4				4.44	

No Understanding	0	0.00
Total	90	100.00

Legends:

Abbreviation	Meaning	Percentage (%)	Range	Verbal Interpretation
RCR	Respondents' Correct Responses	80-100		Very High Understanding (VHU)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	60-79		High Understanding (HU)
SH	School Heads	40-59		Moderate Understanding (MU)
GADC	Gender and Development Coordinators	20-39		Low Understanding (LU)
GADTWG	Gender and Development Technical Working Group	0-19%		Very Low Understanding (VLU)

Table 2 highlights that GAD implementers, including school heads, GAD Coordinators, and GAD TWG members, have a High Understanding (HU) of gender stereotypes and biases, with an overall mean score of 73.92%. The results suggest strong knowledge of policy-level gender issues, especially in advocating for inclusive education. Notably high scores were recorded for questions related to the role of GAD coordinators (97.80%) and collaboration with student organizations (95.60%), indicating familiarity with institutional responsibilities and advocacy.

However, moderate understanding was observed in areas involving the impact of gender bias on student experiences, such as teacher-student interactions (43.00%), career choices (53.30%), and access to extracurricular activities (48.90%). This reveals a gap between policy knowledge and its practical application in everyday school settings.

The findings indicate a clear divide: while respondents excel in policy awareness, they struggle with integrating gender concepts into classroom practices and student engagement. The distribution of understanding levels further reinforces this, with 40% demonstrating Very High Understanding, 34.45% High Understanding, 21.11% Moderate, and 4.45% Low Understanding.

These results underscore the need for more targeted professional development focusing on gender-responsive teaching, teacher training, and student support systems, to bridge the gap between institutional knowledge and practical classroom implementation. These findings support the assertions of Lualhati (2019), who emphasized that gender mainstreaming must go beyond policy adoption and be deeply embedded in classroom instruction, student engagement, and faculty training. Moving forward, schools should focus on integrating gender awareness into professional development programs, student support systems, and teacher evaluation processes to ensure that knowledge translates into practice.

Table 3

Level of Implementation of Policies, Programs and Activities in Governance and Instruction

Governance	Mean			Total Mean	SD	VI
	SH	GADC	GADTWG			

1. There are specific policies in place within school that promote gender equality and inclusivity in decision-making processes.	3.47	3.70	3.47	3.54	0.544	FI
2. Gender perspectives are integrated into the school's strategic planning and decision-making processes.	3.57	3.77	3.63	3.66	0.478	FI
3. There are mechanisms in place to ensure the participation of all genders as school governance and leadership roles.	3.63	3.83	3.63	3.70	0.485	FI
4. School address gender-based violence and harassment in the school environment	3.73	3.87	3.80	3.80	0.402	FI
5. School provides training on gender sensitivity and inclusivity for school administrators and staff.	3.73	3.93	3.67	3.78	0.444	FI
6. Gender perspectives considered in curriculum development and teaching practices within the school.	3.63	3.70	3.47	3.60	0.493	FI
7. There are initiatives in place to promote gender equality in student representation in decision-making bodies within the school.	3.53	3.50	3.57	3.53	0.603	FI
8. School addresses the specific needs and challenges faced by LGBTQ+ students in school governance and policies.	3.40	3.57	3.30	3.42	0.793	FI
9. Different measures are in place to ensure equal access to educational opportunities and resources for all genders within your school.	3.53	3.57	3.43	3.51	0.623	FI
10. School engages with parents and the community to promote gender equality and inclusivity in school governance.	3.47	3.73	3.40	3.53	0.657	FI
11. School ensures that gender perspectives are integrated into the recruitment and promotion processes for school staff.	3.47	3.7	3.43	3.53	0.584	FI
12. Initiatives are in place to address traditional gender biases and stereotypes in the school environment.	3.47	3.67	3.37	3.50	0.640	FI
13. School ensures that all genders have equal access to leadership opportunities and roles within the school governance structure?	3.70	3.80	3.70	3.73	0.445	FI
14. There are specific programs or initiatives aimed at promoting girls' education and empowerment within your school's governance framework.	3.40	3.53	3.57	3.50	0.604	FI
15. School addresses the intersectionality of gender with other factors such as socioeconomic status, ethnicity, and disability in school governance and decision-making.	3.60	3.70	3.47	3.59	0.616	FI
16. School has a system in place to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of Gender and Development initiatives in school governance.	3.43	3.60	3.30	3.44	0.620	FI

17.	School addresses the specific needs of pregnant and parenting students within the school governance structure.	3.43	3.47	3.33	3.41	0.733	FI
18.	There are initiatives in place to promote gender-responsive budgeting and resource allocation within your school's governance framework.	3.50	3.60	3.43	3.51	0.691	FI
19.	School addresses the specific needs of transgender and gender non-conforming students in school policies and programs.	3.10	3.23	3.00	3.11	0.841	MI
20.	There are collaborations with local organizations and government agencies to further promote gender equality and development initiatives within the school governance structure.	3.47	3.67	3.40	3.51	0.658	FI
21.	Gender perspectives are integrated into the curriculum across different subjects in the school.	3.37	3.63	3.50	3.50	0.658	FI
22.	Specific initiatives are in place to address gender stereotypes and biases in classroom teaching materials and resources.	3.40	3.60	3.53	3.51	0.623	FI
23.	School ensures that teaching methods and strategies are gender-responsive and inclusive of diverse gender identities.	3.47	3.70	3.50	3.56	0.620	FI
24.	School provides training and professional development opportunities for teachers on gender-sensitive and inclusive teaching practices.	3.47	3.63	3.67	3.59	0.634	FI
25.	Gender issues and topics related to Gender and Development are integrated into classroom discussions and activities.	3.40	3.7	3.53	3.54	0.656	FI
26.	Programs or initiatives that promote gender equality and women's empowerment through class projects and assignments.	3.37	3.7	3.50	3.52	0.753	FI
27.	School addresses the specific needs of female students in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) subjects and activities.	3.20	3.00	2.93	3.04	0.82	MI
28.	There are initiatives to promote gender equality and respect for diverse gender identities through extracurricular activities and school events.	3.43	3.40	3.40	3.41	0.701	FI
29.	School ensures that learning materials and examples used in class are inclusive and representative of diverse gender identities and experiences.	3.53	3.67	3.60	3.60	0.596	FI
30.	There are measures in place to ensure equal participation and engagement of all students in classroom discussions and activities regardless of gender.	3.57	3.73	3.60	3.63	0.507	FI

31. The school address issues of gender-based violence and discrimination in class instruction and interactions among students.	3.53	3.80	3.67	3.67	0.474	FI
32. There are programs or initiatives to promote gender equality and social justice through service-learning projects and community engagement activities.	3.47	3.80	3.53	3.60	0.596	FI
33. The school ensures that assessments and evaluations are free from gender biases and stereotypes.	3.50	3.80	3.80	3.70	0.507	FI
34. There are mechanisms in place to involve parents and the community in promoting gender equality and development through class activities and projects.	3.43	3.47	3.33	3.41	0.616	FI
35. School addresses the specific needs of LGBTQ+ students in class instruction and support services?	3.40	3.77	3.47	3.54	0.603	FI
36. The school addresses the needs of students with diverse gender identities and expressions in creating a safe and inclusive classroom environment.	3.47	3.70	3.50	3.56	0.583	FI
37. There are initiatives in place to provide mentorship and support for female students interested in non-traditional fields and career paths.	3.40	3.60	3.57	3.52	0.585	FI
38. The school ensures that classroom discussions and activities promote critical thinking and reflection on gender equality and social justice issues.	3.53	3.63	3.50	3.56	0.522	FI
39. There are programs or initiatives to engage students in advocating for gender equality and social change within the school and the community.	3.47	3.70	3.57	3.58	0.58	FI
40. School measure and evaluate the impact of Gender and Development initiatives on students' attitudes, behaviors, and academic performance.	3.37	3.50	3.40	3.42	0.687	FI
Weighted Mean Interpretation	3.44	3.63	3.51	3.52	0.616	FI
Grand Mean Interpretation	3.48	3.64	3.49	3.54	0.607	FI

Legend:

Abbreviation	Meaning	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
<i>M</i>	<i>Mean</i>	3.25 - 4.00	Fully Implemented (FI)
<i>SD</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	2.50 - 3.24	Moderately Implemented (MI)
<i>VI</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	1.75 - 2.49	Partially Implemented (PI)
<i>SH</i>	<i>School Heads</i>	1.00 - 1.74	Not Implemented (NI)
<i>GADC</i>	<i>Gender and Development Coordinators</i>		
<i>GADTWG</i>	<i>Gender and Development Technical Working Group</i>		

The study revealed that gender mainstreaming in public school governance and classroom instruction is fully implemented, with an overall composite mean of 3.54. This indicates a strong institutional commitment to gender-inclusive policies and practices, particularly in areas such as leadership opportunities, professional development, and addressing gender-based violence. The highest-rated practices include training administrators on gender sensitivity, ensuring equal access to leadership roles, and addressing gender-based harassment. However, challenges remain in addressing the specific needs of LGBTQ+ learners and establishing robust gender-responsive budgeting mechanisms, highlighting areas where inclusivity still needs strengthening.

Notable differences emerged among the perceptions of School Heads (SH), Gender and Development Coordinators (GADC), and Gender and Development Technical Working Group (GADTWG) members. GADC respondents consistently provided higher ratings, suggesting that those directly involved in implementing GAD programs perceive these efforts as more successful. In contrast, SH and GADTWG members, who may encounter broader operational challenges, reported slightly lower ratings. These differences emphasize the need for strengthened communication and collaboration among all stakeholders to ensure a shared understanding of progress and remaining gaps in gender mainstreaming.

In classroom instruction, gender mainstreaming was also rated as fully implemented, with a composite mean of 3.52. Schools have made significant strides in applying gender-sensitive pedagogy, integrating gender concepts into lessons, and promoting equitable learning opportunities. However, challenges persist in STEM subjects and in the consistent monitoring and evaluation of GAD-related instruction. Lower ratings in these areas suggest the need for targeted programs that encourage female and gender-diverse participation in STEM and more systematic assessment of gender-sensitive practices. These findings underscore the importance of continuous training, external partnerships, and data-driven evaluation to sustain and advance gender equity efforts in schools.

Part II. Problems Encountered in Gender and Development Mainstreaming Practices

Table 4

Problems Encountered in Gender and Development Mainstreaming Practices

Indicator	Mean			Total Mean	SD	VI
	SH	GADC	GADTWG			
1. Lack of Awareness- One of the primary challenges in Gender Mainstreaming is the lack of awareness and understanding of gender issues among stakeholders, leading to resistance or apathy towards implementing gender-responsive policies and programs.	2.57	2.63	2.77	2.66	0.938	ModE

2. Inadequate Resources-Limited financial, human, and technological resources can hinder the effective implementation of Gender Mainstreaming practices, resulting in incomplete or ineffective initiatives.	3.00	2.77	2.90	2.89	0.841	ModE
3. Resistance to Change- Resistance to changing traditional gender roles and norms can impede Gender Mainstreaming efforts, as individuals or institutions may be reluctant to challenge existing power structures and biases.	2.43	2.53	2.40	2.46	0.938	LessE
4. Gender Bias and Stereotypes- Deep-rooted gender biases and stereotypes can influence decision-making processes, curriculum development, and resource allocation, hindering the achievement of gender equality goals.	2.57	2.43	2.50	2.50	1.03	ModE
5. Insufficient Training- Lack of appropriate training and capacity-building programs for educators, policymakers, and other stakeholders can prevent the successful integration of gender perspectives in policies and practices.	2.50	2.30	2.50	2.43	1.028	ModE
6. Data Collection Challenges-Inadequate data collection systems and methodologies may result in a lack of gender-disaggregated data, making it difficult to monitor and evaluate the impact of Gender Mainstreaming initiatives.	2.50	2.43	2.27	2.40	0.804	LessE
7. Policy Implementation Gaps-Despite having gender-responsive policies in place, there may be gaps in their implementation due to a lack of clear guidelines, accountability mechanisms, or monitoring frameworks.	2.63	2.43	2.47	2.51	0.89	ModE
8. Intersectionality Challenges- Addressing intersectionality issues, such as the overlapping impacts of gender with other factors like race, ethnicity, class, and disability, can be complex and require a nuanced approach that is often overlooked.	2.57	2.30	2.37	2.41	0.898	LessE
9. Institutional Resistance- Institutional resistance to change, bureaucratic hurdles, and a lack of commitment from leadership can obstruct efforts to mainstream gender equality in organizational practices and culture.	2.47	2.37	2.37	2.40	0.872	LessE
10. Inadequate Evaluation- Limited evaluation mechanisms to assess the effectiveness of Gender Mainstreaming initiatives can make it challenging to measure progress, identify areas for improvement, and ensure accountability.	2.60	2.37	2.37	2.44	0.809	LessE

11. Limited Political Will- Insufficient commitment from government authorities and policymakers to prioritize gender equality and mainstream gender perspectives in policies and programs can hinder effective Gender Mainstreaming practices.	2.50	2.33	2.47	2.43	0.875	LessE
12. Cultural and Social Norms- Deeply ingrained cultural beliefs, social norms, and traditions that perpetuate gender inequalities can pose significant barriers to challenging and changing gender roles and stereotypes.	2.50	2.47	2.53	2.50	0.838	ModE
13. Inadequate Research and Data- A lack of comprehensive research and data on gender issues, particularly in specific contexts or marginalized populations, can impede evidence-based decision-making and hinder targeted interventions.	2.63	2.47	2.40	2.50	0.118	ModE
14. Institutional Inertia- Resistance to change within institutions, bureaucratic red tape, and rigid organizational structures can slow down the implementation of Gender Mainstreaming practices and limit progress towards gender equality.	2.53	2.37	2.47	2.46	0.081	LessE
15. Lack of Gender-Responsive Policies: Absence of gender-responsive policies, or policies that are not effectively implemented or enforced, can undermine efforts to mainstream gender equality and inclusivity in all areas of governance and decision-making.	2.47	2.40	2.40	2.42	0.04	LessE
16. Power Dynamics and Inequality- Power imbalances based on gender, race, class, or other factors can perpetuate inequality and discrimination, making it challenging to create an environment that is truly equitable and inclusive for all individuals.	2.50	2.53	2.30	2.44	0.125	LessE
17. Resource Constraints- Limited financial resources, inadequate staffing, and lack of access to training and capacity-building programs can hinder the successful implementation of Gender Mainstreaming initiatives and limit their impact.	2.57	2.40	2.50	2.49	0.085	LessE
18. Gender Digital Divide- Disparities in access to technology, digital literacy, and online resources based on gender can exacerbate inequalities and limit the effectiveness of Gender Mainstreaming efforts in the digital age.	2.60	2.40	2.37	2.46	0.125	LessE
19. Lack of Intersectoral Collaboration- Siloed approaches and lack of collaboration between different sectors and agencies can lead to fragmented efforts in mainstreaming	2.47	2.40	2.33	2.40	0.070	LessE

gender perspectives, reducing the overall impact of gender equality initiatives.

20. Resistance from Traditional Institutions: Resistance from traditional institutions, such as religious organizations, educational institutions, and community groups, to challenge gender norms and practices can hinder progress towards gender equality and social change	2.47	2.37	2.37	2.40	0.058	LessE
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Weighted Mean	2.55	2.44	2.45			
Interpretation	ModE	LessE	LessE	2.48	0.573	LessE

Legend:

Abbreviation	Meaning	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
SD	Standard Deviation	3.25 - 4.00	Mostly Encountered (MosE)
VI	Verbal Interpretation	2.50 - 3.24	Moderately Encountered (ModE)
SH	School Heads	1.75 - 2.49	Less Encountered (LessE)
GADC	Gender and Development Coordinators	1.00 - 1.74	Least Encountered (LeastE)
GADTWG	Gender and Development Technical Working Group		

Based on the findings in Table 4, the most moderately encountered problem in Gender and Development (GAD) mainstreaming practices is inadequate resources, which scored the highest total mean of 2.89. This indicates that limited financial, human, and technological resources are a significant challenge in implementing effective GAD initiatives. This lack of resources often leads to incomplete or underdeveloped programs, hindering the overall goal of gender equality. Furthermore, lack of awareness (2.66) and gender bias and stereotypes (2.50) are also moderately encountered, suggesting that despite efforts, there are still persistent issues in stakeholder knowledge and mindset, which can negatively affect the success of GAD integration in schools and institutions.

However, the overall weighted mean of 2.48 falls within the "Less Encountered" category, indicating that most of the problems listed are not heavily experienced by respondents. School Heads reported a slightly higher perception of encountering problems (2.55, ModE), while Gender and Development Coordinators (2.44) and Technical Working Groups (2.45) rated these issues as less frequently encountered. This discrepancy may reflect different levels of involvement and exposure to the challenges of implementing GAD programs. For example, School Heads may face more administrative constraints and community resistance than coordinators who are more focused on program design and monitoring.

Several indicators scored particularly low, such as lack of gender-responsive policies, institutional inertia, and resistance from traditional institutions, all falling below a mean of 2.46 and categorized as "Less Encountered." These findings suggest that while structural and cultural barriers to GAD still exist, their impact may not be as pressing or widely perceived compared to logistical and capacity-related challenges. Despite these issues being rated lower, their cumulative effect should not be overlooked, as they can silently undermine long-term progress. Thus, continuous

capacity-building, resource allocation, and stakeholder engagement remain essential to address both the visible and underlying barriers to effective gender mainstreaming.

Part III. Solutions Applied by GAD Implementers to Address the Problems Encountered

Table 5

Solutions Applied by GAD Implementers to Address Problems Encountered

Solutions	Mean			Total Mean	SD	VI
	SH	GADC	GADTWG			
<i>A. Community Partnership</i>						
1. Collaborating with other organizations, community groups, or government agencies to share costs and resources, maximizing the impact of GAD initiatives despite limited budgets.	3.47	3.50	3.47	3.48	0.64	MosA
2. Engaging volunteers from the community or recruiting local champions passionate about gender equality to supplement manpower and reduce program costs.	3.50	3.43	3.50	3.48	0.64	MosA
3. Investing in capacity building for school personnel to empower them to take on roles and responsibilities within GAD initiatives, reducing the need for external consultants or costly experts.	3.63	3.57	3.73	3.64	0.567	MosA
4. Building alliances with local leaders, traditional authorities, religious institutions, and community organizations, collaborating with influential figures to promote positive messages and advocate for gender equality within cultural contexts.	3.53	3.53	3.50	3.52	0.691	MosA
5. Highlighting and celebrating positive role models who challenge gender stereotypes, showcasing stories of individuals who have defied cultural norms to achieve success and contribute positively to their communities.	3.60	3.60	3.57	3.59	0.579	MosA
6. Initiating open and respectful dialogues with community members, leaders, and influencers to understand the roots of cultural norms and beliefs that perpetuate gender	3.57	3.47	3.53	3.52	0.691	MosA

inequality, raising awareness about the impact of these norms and promoting discussions on alternative perspectives.

Weighted Mean Interpretation	3.55 MosA	3.52 MosA	3.55 MosA	3.54	0.63	MosA
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Solutions	Mean			Total Mean	SD	VI
	SH	GADC	GADTWG			
<i>B. Financial Resources</i>						
1. Advocating for organizations' or governments' adoption of gender-responsive budgeting practices to ensure the school's budget addresses different genders' specific needs and priorities and promotes gender equality.	3.50	3.60	3.43	3.51	0.640	MosA
2. Actively seeking alternative funding sources through grants, partnerships with donor agencies, or collaboration with private sector organizations that support gender-focused initiatives.	3.50	3.67	3.67	3.61	0.555	MosA
3. Exploring innovative financing models such as social impact bonds, crowdfunding, or community-based financing to provide alternative funding sources for GAD programs.	3.50	3.47	3.5	3.49	0.674	MosA
Weighted Mean Interpretation	3.50 MosA	3.58 MosA	3.53 MosA	3.54	0.623	MosA
<i>C. Communication and Technology</i>						
1. Leveraging technology such as online platforms, social media, and digital tools to reduce administrative costs, reach wider audiences, and improve program implementation and monitoring efficiency.	3.43	3.43	3.33	3.40	0.70	MosA
Weighted Mean Interpretation	3.43 MosA	3.43 MosA	3.33 MosA	3.40	0.70	MosA

D. Curriculum

1. Redesigning programs to be more cost-effective while still achieving objectives, involving prioritizing activities with the highest impact, streamlining processes, or leveraging existing resources and infrastructure.	3.40	3.40	3.40	3.40	0.667	MosA
2. Implementing targeted education and awareness campaigns, organizing workshops, seminars, and community events to educate individuals about gender equality, human rights, and the benefits of gender-inclusive societies.	3.67	3.60	3.50	3.59	0.634	MosA

Solutions	Mean			Total Mean	SD	VI
	SH	GADC	GADTWG			
3. Tailoring interventions and programs to align with local customs and traditions, engaging community members in designing and implementing initiatives to ensure relevance and cultural sensitivity.	3.63	3.57	3.60	3.60	0.557	MosA
4. Investing in the empowerment of women and girls through education, skills training, and economic opportunities to challenge traditional gender roles and demonstrate the benefits of gender equality within communities.	3.60	3.63	3.53	3.59	0.559	MosA
Weighted Mean Interpretation	3.58 MosA	3.55 MosA	3.51 MosA	3.55	0.604	MosA

<i>E. Monitoring and Evaluation</i>						
1. Implementing robust monitoring and evaluation systems to identify inefficiencies and areas for improvement, enabling focal persons to optimize resource allocation and demonstrate impact to stakeholders.	3.40	3.47	3.33	3.40	0.70	MosA
2. Identifying and addressing the underlying drivers of resistance	3.53	3.47	3.57	3.52	0.674	MosA

towards gender equality, including fear of change, economic insecurities, or misconceptions about gender roles, to foster more inclusive attitudes.	Weighted Mean Interpretation	3.47 MosA	3.47 MosA	3.45 MosA	3.46	0.687	MosA
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Continuation of Table 6. (Solutions)

<i>F. Capacity Building</i>							
1. Investing in capacity building for students will empower them to take on roles and responsibilities within GAD initiatives, reducing the need for external consultants or costly experts.	3.63	3.63	3.53	3.59	0.559	MosA	
2. Building the capacity of community members, especially women and youth, to become change agents and advocates for gender equality creates a ripple effect within societies.	3.70	3.63	3.70	3.68	0.557	MosA	
Weighted Mean Interpretation	3.65 MosA	3.63 MosA	3.62 MosA	3.64	0.56	MosA	

Solutions	Mean			Total Mean	SD	VI
	SH	GADC	GADTWG			
<i>G. Policy Formulation</i>						
1. Advocating for policy reforms that allocate more resources towards gender equality initiatives, engaging policymakers, conducting research to demonstrate the economic benefits of gender equality, and mobilizing public support.	3.57	3.43	3.50	3.50	0.623	MosA
2. Advocating legal and policy reforms that protect women's rights and promote gender equality, engaging policymakers and lawmakers to enact and enforce laws that challenge discriminatory cultural practices.	3.60	3.47	3.60	3.56	0.62	MosA
Weighted Mean Interpretation	3.59 MosA	3.45 MosA	3.60 MosA	3.53	0.60	MosA

Combined Weighted Mean Interpretation		3.54 MosA	3.52 MosA	3.51 MosA	3.52	0.63	MosA
Legend:							
Abbreviation	Meaning	Score Range		Verbal Interpretation			
<i>M</i>	<i>Mean</i>	3.25 - 4.00		<i>Mostly Applied (MosA)</i>			
<i>SD</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	2.50 - 3.24		<i>Moderately Applied (ModA)</i>			
<i>VI</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	1.75 - 2.49		<i>Less Applied (LessA)</i>			
<i>SH</i>	<i>School Heads</i>	1.00 - 1.74		<i>Least Applied (LeastA)</i>			
<i>GADC</i>	<i>Gender and Development Coordinators</i>						
<i>GADTWG</i>	<i>Gender and Development Technical Working Group</i>						

The table 5 summarizes various solutions applied by Gender and Development (GAD) implementers, including School Heads (SH), Gender and Development Coordinators (GADC), and Gender and Development Technical Working Groups (GADTWG), to address challenges encountered in their programs. Across all solution categories—Community Partnership, Financial Resources, Communication and Technology, Curriculum, Monitoring and Evaluation, Capacity Building, and Policy Formulation—the overall mean ratings fall within the "Mostly Applied" (MosA) range. This indicates that these groups are generally proactive and effective in adopting a broad range of strategies to overcome obstacles in implementing GAD initiatives. Notably, solutions related to Community Partnership and Capacity Building received some of the highest mean scores, reflecting the emphasis on collaboration with external stakeholders and empowerment of internal personnel.

Community partnerships were widely leveraged as a critical approach, with high ratings for collaborating with organizations and community groups, engaging local volunteers, and building alliances with cultural and traditional leaders. These strategies enhance resource sharing, extend program reach, and foster culturally sensitive advocacy for gender equality. Additionally, capacity-building efforts aimed at empowering school personnel, students, and community members emerged as a key tactic to reduce dependence on costly external consultants and to create advocates for gender equality within the community. This focus on internal empowerment ensures sustainability and broadens the impact of GAD initiatives over time.

In terms of financial and policy strategies, GAD implementers actively pursued gender-responsive budgeting, alternative funding mechanisms such as grants and crowdfunding, and advocated for policy reforms to secure dedicated resources and stronger legal protections for women's rights. Communication and technology tools were also moderately applied, primarily to reduce costs and improve program delivery efficiency. Curriculum adaptations focused on tailoring interventions to local contexts and prioritizing cost-effective, impactful activities. Monitoring and evaluation mechanisms, while less emphasized than partnerships or capacity building, were still recognized as important for identifying inefficiencies and addressing resistance to gender equality. Overall, the consistently "Mostly Applied" rating across categories

reflects a comprehensive, multifaceted approach by GAD implementers to sustain and strengthen gender equality programs despite various challenges.

PART IV. Proposed Gender Mainstreaming Plan to Enhance Gender Mainstreaming Practices

The findings of the study indicate that gender mainstreaming in public schools in Alabat Island is hindered by several barriers, with a composite mean of 2.48, suggesting that these challenges are moderately encountered across different stakeholders. The most pressing issues include limited financial and human resources (mean: 2.89), low awareness of gender-related concepts (mean: 2.66), and cultural and societal norms that reinforce gender biases (mean: 2.50). These factors negatively affect the full implementation of gender-responsive policies and practices, making it necessary to enhance the existing gender mainstreaming framework.

This plan is proposed to directly address the findings of the study by ensuring that gender mainstreaming is comprehensive, well-funded, integrated into school governance, and continuously monitored and evaluated. The proposed interventions focus on capacity building, policy development, community engagement, and systematic evaluation, aligning with national mandates (RA 9710 – Magna Carta of Women, DepEd Gender-Responsive Basic Education Policy, and Sustainable Development Goal 5 on Gender Equality).

Objectives of the Enhanced Gender Mainstreaming Plan

1. Increase Gender Awareness and Sensitivity among teachers, students, and school stakeholders through structured training programs.
2. Strengthening Policy Implementation by reviewing, revising, and enforcing gender-responsive policies.
3. Ensure Adequate Funding and Resources for sustainable gender initiatives in schools.
4. Enhance Community Engagement by involving parents, local government units (LGUs), and community organizations.
5. Establish a Monitoring and Evaluation System to track progress, identify gaps, and continuously improve gender mainstreaming efforts.

Intervention Program: Enhanced Gender Mainstreaming Plan

This intervention program integrates the four key components of a Monitoring and Evaluation Plan:

1. Inputs – Resources needed (e.g., budget, personnel, training materials)
2. Activities – Specific actions to be implemented
3. Outputs – Immediate deliverables or results
4. Outcomes – Long-term impact of the program

1. Capacity Building and Training

Monitoring and Evaluation Plan Components	Details
Inputs	Funding for workshops, training materials, gender experts, online learning modules
Activities	Conduct gender sensitivity workshops for teachers and school staff Integrate gender-responsive pedagogy into teacher

Monitoring and Evaluation Details
Plan Components

Outputs	training Develop online modules for continuous learning Increased teacher participation in gender awareness programs Production of instructional guides on gender-responsive teaching
Outcomes	Enhanced gender-sensitive teaching strategies in classrooms Improved knowledge and confidence among teachers in implementing gender-responsive policies

The study found that lack of awareness (mean: 2.66) and insufficient training (mean: 2.43) hinder gender mainstreaming. This intervention ensures that all educators are equipped with gender-sensitive knowledge and skills.

2. Policy Development and Strengthening

Monitoring and Evaluation Details
Plan Components

Inputs	Policy review team, legal experts, consultation meetings, policy framework resources
Activities	Conduct a review of existing gender policies Develop new policies based on identified gaps Establish clear accountability measures for policy enforcement
Outputs	Revised gender-responsive school policies Approved and disseminated guidelines for gender inclusion in school governance Stronger institutional commitment to gender mainstreaming
Outcomes	Elimination of policy implementation gaps A safer and more inclusive school environment

The study found policy implementation gaps (mean: 2.51) as a barrier to gender mainstreaming. This intervention ensures that policies are well-defined, actionable, and consistently enforced.

3. Resource Mobilization and Funding for Gender Initiatives

Monitoring and Evaluation Details
Plan Components

Inputs	Budget allocation, local government funding, partnerships with NGOs and private organizations
Activities	Conduct gender-responsive budgeting (GRB) workshops Develop grant proposals for funding support

**Monitoring and Evaluation Details
Plan Components**

Outputs	Engage private sector partners and local businesses in supporting gender initiatives Secured funding for gender programs Increased budget allocation for gender-related activities
Outcomes	Sustainable financial support for gender initiatives More schools implementing gender-responsive programs without resource constraints

The study found that financial limitations (mean: 2.89) were the most significant challenge. This component ensures that gender mainstreaming programs are financially sustainable.

4. Community Engagement and Advocacy

**Monitoring and Evaluation Details
Plan Components**

Inputs	Community leaders, parents, advocacy groups, social media platforms
Activities	Conduct community forums on gender awareness Implement parent education programs on gender sensitivity Establish communication channels for gender advocacy (social media, radio, community meetings) Conduct ongoing evaluation and improvement activities
Outputs	Increased community participation in gender initiatives Greater parental involvement in school-based gender programs
Outcomes	A school-community partnership that promotes gender equality Reduced gender biases in school, households and local communities

The study found that cultural norms (mean: 2.50) and Gender Bias and Stereotypes (mean: 2.50) can pose significant barriers to challenging and changing gender roles and stereotypes. By engaging communities in gender awareness programs and continuously evaluating their efforts, these barriers can be systematically addressed and make adjustments as needed.

5. Data Collection

**Monitoring and Evaluation Plan Details
Components**

Inputs	Research and disaggregated data
Activities	Administered online, paper, interviews or surveys

Monitoring and Evaluation Plan Details Components

	Access school records, such as attendance data, grades, and standardized test scores that can provide valuable insights. However, researchers must ensure they comply with privacy regulations and obtain appropriate permissions.
	Observing classroom interactions, student behavior, and school environment
	Conduct focus groups and individual interviews allow for deeper exploration of student perspectives, experiences, and challenges ¹⁰ .
Outputs	Collection of research and disaggregated data from schools while upholding ethical standards and protecting student privacy.
Outcomes	Ongoing data collection and analysis, allowing for continuous improvement and better understanding of student needs

The study found that a lack of comprehensive data on gender issues (2.50), particularly in specific contexts or marginalized populations, can impede evidence-based decision-making and hinder targeted interventions. Collection of information can be invaluable for improving educational practices, addressing disparities, and ensuring that all students have the opportunity to succeed.

Conclusions

Based on the given findings, the following conclusions were made:

1. The findings indicate that awareness of Gender and Development (GAD) mainstreaming among school stakeholders is high, particularly in policy-related concepts and institutional responsibilities. However, while gender-responsive policies are widely recognized, gaps persist in their practical application, especially in gender-sensitive pedagogy, decision-making, and financial compliance. The inconsistent integration of gender concepts into classroom instruction and governance structures suggests that existing policies have not been fully translated into daily educational practices. This highlights the need for targeted training programs, enhanced monitoring mechanisms, and strengthened institutional support to ensure that gender mainstreaming moves beyond policy recognition and is effectively implemented across all aspects of school leadership and instruction.
2. The implementation of GAD mainstreaming practices in the management of public schools is also at a full level, with stronger policy integration into governance but weaker application in instructional materials and classroom practices. Schools have established gender policies, but the extent to which

these policies translate into concrete actions in teaching and learning remains limited.

3. Challenges in GAD implementation primarily stem from resource constraints. Financial limitations hinder the sustainability of gender programs, while gender bias and stereotype and traditional gender norms slow the adoption of gender-responsive practices. Policy enforcement gaps further limit the long-term success of these initiatives.
4. The developed Gender Mainstreaming Plan directly addresses these challenges by strengthening capacity-building programs, reinforcing policy implementation, securing funding and resources, and enhancing stakeholder engagement. These interventions provide a structured approach to improving gender awareness, expanding gender-sensitive teaching strategies, and ensuring that gender policies are effectively enforced across all levels of school governance.

Recommendations

To address the identified challenges and ensure effective GAD mainstreaming in schools, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. In response to the first findings, which highlights the gaps in the practical application of gender-responsive policies, the integration of gender concepts in educational practice may be strengthened through continuous training programs tailored to real-life classroom scenarios. A structured mentorship program pairing experienced GAD coordinators with those who have limited exposure can enhance knowledge-sharing and practical application.
2. Building on the second findings that points to the limited translation of established gender policies into concrete actions, targeted workshops may be developed to help school stakeholders identify and address traditional gender stereotypes and biases. Collaborating with gender studies experts can provide educators with effective strategies and tools to challenge biases in both classroom instruction and school decision-making.
3. Addressing the challenges noted in the third conclusion regarding resource constraints and policy enforcement gaps, monitoring and evaluation mechanisms may need to be reinforced to ensure the consistent implementation of gender-sensitive policies. Engaging teachers, parents, and community leaders in policy enforcement will foster a collaborative commitment to gender inclusivity and help overcome cultural resistance.
4. In line with the findings that emphasizes the need for stronger support systems, addressing financial limitations requires dedicated funding for gender-responsive initiatives and stronger partnerships with NGOs, local government units, and private organizations. Community outreach programs may be implemented to promote gender inclusivity and encourage collective support for GAD initiatives.
5. GAD implementers in Alabat Island's public schools are encouraged to the complete adoption and implementation of the newly developed Gender Mainstreaming Plan. Alabat Island's public schools must fully implement the new

Gender Mainstreaming Plan to address the gap between GAD policy awareness and its practical application. The plan strengthens capacity, improves gender-sensitive practices, secures resources, and fosters collaboration to achieve sustainable gender equality in education.

6. While the study focused on the status of GAD mainstreaming practices in the management of public schools based on the perspective of GAD Implementers, it lacked data on how gender mainstreaming affected teachers not directly involved. The need for a broader impact assessment, understanding how gender mainstreaming affects teacher attitudes, workload, and professional development, may be necessary. Therefore, further research is recommended to examine the impact of gender mainstreaming on teachers who are not directly involved in GAD implementation. Investigating how gender mainstreaming affects teacher attitudes, workload, and professional development can provide valuable insights for refining existing practices and improving the overall inclusivity of the educational environment.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors of this study affirm their full compliance with ethical standards in the conduct of the research. All procedures involving participants were carried out with respect for their rights, privacy, and confidentiality. The study adhered to relevant ethical guidelines and obtained necessary approvals from appropriate institutional review boards or ethics committees. Informed consent was secured from all participants, and data were handled responsibly to ensure integrity and transparency throughout the research process.

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